

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**RATE AND SEVERITY OF DEPRESSION JUST AFTER THE
DEMISE OF SPOUSE**¹Dr. Maria Batool, ²Dr. Samiullah Khan, ³Dr. Irtesam Tahir¹Punjab Medical College Faisalabad, ²Shandong Medical University China, ³Punjab Medical College Faisalabad.**Article Received:** March 2019**Accepted:** April 2019**Published:** May 2019**Abstract:**

Background: The prevalence of depression in latter age is the cause of various complications. Mostly, people above the age fifty five years have mental abnormalities which is not common in the process of ageing. Majority of people of this age fell satisfaction and handle the ageing process.

Objective: This case work aimed to evaluate the rate and severity of the despair and depression in first 3 months after the demise of spouse.

Study Design: This was a descriptive case work conducted in hospital.

Venue & duration: The case work carried out in Psychiatry department of Jinnah Hospital Lahore & Ahbab Hospital Lahore. This case work started in May 2018 and lasted up to November 2018.

Methodology: Total 107 patients from both genders having age from 45-65 years of age facing the complication of depression detected on the basis of standard of DSM-IV after the death of their spouse within last 3 months evaluated for the extremity of the symptoms of depression with the utilization of the HAM-D which is Hamilton rating scale for depression. We conducted an interview to gather the detail about demography.

Results: Seventy seven percent males and 19.0% females got the scores of severity level in scored in Hamilton rating scale for depression in the period of first 3 months after spouse death. Thinking about suicide and less compliance to medicines are present highly among male patients in comparison with the females.

Conclusion: The prevalence of depression is much frequent after the spouse death & professionals in this field should make proper procedure to enhance the QoL (Quality of Life) of these patients in their elderly age.

Keywords: HAM-D, despair, depression, spouse, demise, venue, methodology, suicide, spouse.

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Please cite this article in press Maria Batool et al., *Rate and Severity of Depression Just after the Demise of Spouse.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(05).

INTRODUCTION:

The incidence depression in elderly age is very frequent mental health issue. About 1/5th persons having age more than fifty five years are suffering from mental abnormalities [1]. Most of the persons cope with the process of aging & many show their satisfaction. But it is a concerning matter in the minds of professionals as well as common population to accept the less functioning and more health issue among people with old age [2]. Main syndrome of depression are very prevalent, persistent & disabling in the period of bereavement stress. In one case work, evaluation tree hundred and fifty widows & widowers carried out for the symptoms of depression after 2, 13 & 25 months after demise of spouse. In the same manner, the evaluation of one hundred and twenty six persons from both gender with similar demography carried out. That work discovered that SMD syndrome (Symptomatic Major Depression) & SSD (Subsyndromic Symptomatic Depression) were present in the complete first 2 years of the widowhood & it has association with the high morbidity rate during the initial 2 years of demise [3].

One case work from USA took forty eight adults, spousal caregivers of hospice parents & thirty six healthy controls. Like in the current case work, the authors in the past case work took HAM-D for the extremity of the condition of depression. The findings concluded that depression as well as other indices of the metal problems are very high during the period of care giving especially within few months after the demise, before reducing over the period of 1st year [4]. Self-reported procedures of stress, depression and grief were under consideration among widows & widowers for more than 2.50 years duration after the demise of life partner I the state of California, USA. The findings showed that grief experience persists for minimum thirty months in male and female with elderly age who have lost their life partner [5]. On other case work displayed that co-morbid clinical conditions, propensity of the patients to somatise, cognitive decline, and different events in life as bereavement, moving in small house, retirement from job all further obfuscate the process of diagnosis [6]. All of the mentioned factors lead to the mental

anomalies. This current case work aimed to evaluate the rate and extremity of the depression within 3 months after the demise of the spouse.

METHODOLOGY:

This case work is descriptive research work based on hospital work. This case work conducted in Psychiatry department in Jinnah Hospital Lahore & Ahbab Hospital in the same city. This case work started in May 2018 and finished in November 2018. There were total one hundred and seven participants of this case work from both genders. The range of the age of participants was from 45 years to 65 years. They suffering from the depression as detected by Psychiatrist in accordance with the DSM-IV a standard for measuring the depression. The spouses of these patients had died in last three months.

The patients suffering from extreme physical complications & co-morbid psychiatric abnormalities were no the part of this case work. We conducted an interview for the collection of data about demography of the patients after getting their verbal willing. HAM-D scale was in use for the evaluation of the extremity of the complication of depression.

RESULTS:

Out of 107 patients, 65.0% (n: 70) participants were males & 35.0% (n: 37) patients were females. The average age of the patients was 54.4 ± 7.62 years. Seventy eight (73.0%) patients belonged to the city areas and twenty nine patients (27.0%) were from the non-urban areas. Twenty six patients (24.0%) found with no education, fifty three (330%) patients have complete 10 year education and forty six (43.0%) patients were graduates. Twenty two patients (21.0%) were performing duties and eighty five (79.0%) patients were available with no employment. Findings show that fifty four males (77.0%) males & seven (19.0%) female got score greater on the scale of HAM-D, while eleven (16.0%) male & eighteen (49.0%) females were suffering from moderate depression and five (7.0%) males & twelve (32.0%) females were suffering from mild depression according to the scale of HAM-D.

Table-I: Percentage of males and females on the three categories of depression

Categories on HAM-D	Male		Female	
	No	Percent	No	Percent
Mild	5.0	7.0	12.0	32.0
Moderate	9.0	13.0	18.0	49.0
Severe	56.0	80.0	7.0	19.0

This shows that most of the males (80.0%) were available with extreme level of depression & most of the females (49.0%) were suffering from the category of moderate depression. This indicates that the occurrence of depression is very high among males in comparison with the females. Out of total participants, twenty eight (40.0%) males & five (14.0%) females stated he ideas of thinking about suicide. Twenty four males (34.0%) & ten (27.0%) females stated the poor compliance of drugs. This shows that these thinking are also more prevalent among males in comparison with the females.

DISCUSSION:

The recent case work displays that the prevalence of depression is very high among male in comparison with females in the period of first three months after the demise of their spouses. The findings of this case work are consistent with the outcome of a case work conducted in California [4]. One case work evaluated the rate of depression within thirteen months after spouse demise. The utilized measures were ZDS (Zung Depression Scale) & HSC (Hopkins Symptoms Checklist). Authors finished evaluation on 3 levels of two, seven & thirteen month after the demise of the spouse [9]. Regardless of different measuring tools the results of that case work are similar with this current study.

On other case work stated that there is a strong association between depression, loss of beloved and attitude towards suicide for both genders. The analysis on the data of demography stated that the idea of suicide was more prevalent among females in

comparison with males [10]. The findings of this case work display that thoughts about the suicide are very common in men as compared to females this outcome is similar with the result of one case work conducted in USA [11]. Recent casework stressed that professionals in the field of mental health should be careful when a patients is reporting about the ideas of suicide after the demise of the spouse. Chentsova in his case work concluded that mental distress indices as depression are very high in the period of just after the demise of the life partner. These results are similar with the outcome of this case work [4]. The occurrence of depression is much frequent after the spouse death in both genders particularly in adults who have past history of depression in their life [9].

There are some limitations of this case work as amount of the female participants was very less 35.0% in comparison with the males as 65.0%. There is also a requirement for future case works enrolling same amount of participants from both genders to determine the occurrence rate and severity of depression after the demise of the spouse.

CONCLUSION:

The findings of this case work increases the vitality of the proper awareness of the caregivers about the patients suffering from the depression after the demise of their life partners. Additionally, physical grievances as concluded by the patients of depression need in time diagnosis as well as management. There is a special need of attention to the male patients suffering after the death of their spouse because of suicidal ideas and worsening condition of their physical health.

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